

Influence of Path–Goal Leadership Styles on Headteachers’ Change Management Strategies in Basic Schools in The Tema Metropolis

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ABSTRACT: The study examined the influence of Path–Goal leadership styles on headteachers’ change management strategies in basic schools within the Tema Metropolis. Guided by the Path–Goal Leadership Theory, a descriptive correlational design and quantitative approach were employed. Data were collected from 125 headteachers using a structured questionnaire with overall Cronbach’s alpha of 0.83. Data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and multiple regression. Findings revealed that supportive leadership was most prevalent ($M = 4.15$), followed by achievement-oriented ($M = 4.05$), participative ($M = 3.98$), and directive leadership ($M = 3.72$). Among change management strategies, communication ($M = 4.14$) and planning ($M = 4.10$) were most emphasized. Regression results showed that supportive leadership most strongly influenced communication ($\beta = 0.45$) and staff involvement ($\beta = 0.42$), while achievement-oriented and participative styles significantly influence planning, monitoring, and collaboration. Directive leadership complemented this influence by providing structure. The study concludes that effective change management depends on balancing supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented behaviors, with directive leadership ensuring clarity. It recommends professional development, increased teacher participation, and mentor-ship programme to enhance adaptive and effective leadership among headteachers.

KEYWORDS: Leadership, Path–Goal, Metropolis, Management, Strategies, Complemented

INTRODUCTION

Leadership is one of the most important aspects of an organization, even in an educational institution. A good leader provides a vision, sets goals, allocates resources, and helps followers stay motivated. As a result, they focus their energy on the attainment of the goals (Bush, 2020; Leithwood et al., 2020). As a part of an educational institution, leadership is much more than the efficiency of administration. It also includes the ability to form cultures of collaboration, to lead the development of teachers, as well as to nurture conditions in which students excel academically and socially. To this end, leadership in a school is instructional and transformational. Headteachers develop an egalitarian approach to leadership. They hold managerial duties where they focus on inspiring change and constant growth (Day & Sammons, 2016; Hallinger, 2021).

Educational systems all over the world are changing because of advancements in technology, policy changes, and market needs in other countries that demand critical reasoning, problem-solving, and skills relevant to the 21st century (Fullan, 2020). Within such a context, line leaders’ ability to foresee, handle, and maintain change has become critical in whether the reforms are implemented successfully or not. Studies by Day and Sammons (2016) and Harris and Jones (2020) argue that schools that do not accommodate particular changes experience a drop in academic performance, lowered teacher morale, failure to engage students, and a resultant increase in poor educational outcomes and inequality in access to education. As noted by Hallinger (2021), leaders who fail to engage staff in the meaningfully change process or adopt inappropriate leadership approaches may construct resistance, diminish teacher commitment, and undermine the reform agenda. On the other hand, leaders who are flexible and adopt relevant leadership approaches are more likely to drive sustainable change, increase teacher empowerment, and improve student outcomes.

In the case of sub-Saharan Africa, the purpose of the introduced educational reforms has been to improve the quality and equity of education. Nevertheless, systemic issues such as inadequate change resistance and the lack of resources and teachers have greatly hampered progress (Osei, 2022; Apau, 2021). The reforms, especially in basic education, are often attributed to the head teachers’ leadership who are the central change leaders in schools (Nguyen et al., 2019). Path Goal leadership theory by House (1971) illustrates the ways in which school leaders are able to change the leadership styles to be more directive, supportive, participative, or achievement oriented to situational demands and enhance staff productivity.

In Ghana, the Ministry of Education alongside Ghana Education Service (GES) has introduced several reforms aimed at improving learning outcomes at the basic education level. These include the introduction of the Common Core Programme (CCP), promotion

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of inclusive education, and attempts to teach with the integration of technology (GES, 2020). These reforms are a worthy cause but, their implementation has been hampered by teacher unpreparedness, scarcity of teaching and learning materials, and resistance to change in the classroom (Ampofo, 2022; Mahama, 2022). Headteachers are expected to fill these voids by practicing dominant leadership styles and change management systems that involve the teachers, parents, and other stakeholders in the reform process (Adu-Gyamfi and Amponsah, 2021). Sufficient change in leadership skills had been observed in headteachers who had received training in change leadership. However, most headteachers had been noted to rely on the unchallenged traditional directive leadership approach (Mensah, 2020; Northouse, 2021). This approach does not tend to foster collaboration or innovation.

The change management issues are most acute in the Tema Metropolis within the context of education in Ghana. In Tema, a population structure with varying socio-economic and ethnic origins is documented, with relative Theory of Schooling covering the Nation’s metropolis Gital School System Doctorate GSS 2021). In particular, metropolitan cities are at the forefront of attempts and challenges to modify the education system of a country, and are, at the same time, expected to fulfil the requirements of the adopting curriculum, fostering improvement in the education standards of the country, motivating the teachers, disciplining the students, and involving parents in the educational process of the children. However, the Tema Education Directorate reports and asserts that some schools have been and are unable to demonstrate and put into practice effective socio-educational leadership in organizing, integrating, and synthesizing the primary tasks of instruction and education. Such a condition is claimed to be fundamental to the differences, detected and proved, in the outcomes achieved by students in varying schools. TME,2022). The socio-economic dynamics of the city along with the concerns and the expectations of the parents and the society about the students’ educational success, and the Achieve of the School, head are believed to be encouraging the assumption of flexible leadership by the head to focus on energizing their schools of change and to foster commitment and gain help to overcome change resistance.

In this case, the Path-Goal Theory of Leadership is employed to understand how headteachers in the town of Tema Metropolis tailor their leadership approaches to the management of change to improvement of the schools’ effectiveness. Some leaders are likely to use negative, command style, leadership approach to compel compliance with the reforms.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Leadership is universally recognized as one of the most significant determinants of institutional success, particularly in education where the performance of schools is closely tied to the quality of leadership exhibited by headteachers (Leithwood et al., 2020; Bush, 2020). Over the past two decades, schools worldwide have faced mounting pressures from rapid educational reforms, curriculum transitions, accountability frameworks, and stakeholder expectations for improved learning outcomes (Fullan, 2020; Hallinger, 2021). These systemic changes demand effective leadership and deliberate change management strategies to maintain teacher morale, strengthen instructional delivery, and achieve sustainable school improvement.

Although leadership and change management have been extensively examined in developed countries, limited attention has been given to how specific leadership theories, such as the Path–Goal theory, apply to basic school administration in developing contexts like Ghana. In recent years, the Ministry of Education and the Ghana Education Service (GES) have rolled out ambitious reforms such as the Standards-Based Curriculum, the Common Core Programme (CCP), and digital tools for school management. While these initiatives are designed to improve teaching and learning, they also present challenges including inadequate resources, teacher resistance, heavy administrative demands, and pressure on headteachers to meet reform expectations (Asare & Nti, 2021; Osei, 2022). Managing such reforms requires leadership that is adaptive, supportive, and participatory. Yet research shows that many school leaders in Ghana still rely on traditional, authoritarian leadership styles that discourage teacher innovation and participation (Somech, 2010; Muindi, 2011). These practices often lead to low teacher motivation, weak reform adoption, and ultimately diminished student achievement.

The Path–Goal theory of leadership, proposed by House (1971), emphasizes the leader’s role in clarifying tasks, removing obstacles, and motivating subordinates toward achieving organizational goals. Its four styles; directive, supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented are meant to be flexibly applied based on staff needs and contextual challenges. International research affirms that leaders who effectively adapt these styles can strengthen teacher collaboration, enhance institutional performance, and improve reform outcomes (Northouse, 2021; Leithwood et al., 2020). However, empirical research examining the use of Path–Goal leadership styles in Ghanaian schools remains limited.

Some local studies have explored leadership and reform challenges broadly. For instance, Osei (2022) investigated headteachers’ experiences in implementing curriculum reforms, while Asare and Nti (2021) assessed the Standards-Based Curriculum and its implications for teaching. Similarly, Ingersoll et al. (2018) and Somech (2010) emphasized the importance of participatory leadership in driving school improvement. Although valuable, these studies did not specifically examine the nexus between Path–Goal leadership styles and headteachers’ change management strategies, particularly within Ghana’s urban, resource-constrained settings.

The case of Tema Metropolis is especially critical. As one of Ghana’s rapidly urbanizing districts, Tema faces unique challenges including overcrowded classrooms due to migration, frequent teacher transfers, limited teaching resources, and heightened pressure

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to deliver on government reforms. These dynamics complicate change management and call for headteachers who can flexibly adapt their leadership style to align teacher motivation with reform demands. Yet anecdotal evidence suggests that many headteachers in the metropolis struggle with adaptive leadership, leading to inconsistent implementation of reforms and uneven student outcomes. While leadership and reform have been studied separately, little research has focused on the intersection of Path–Goal leadership theory and change management within the distinctive socio-educational context of Tema Metropolis.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The study sought to investigate influence of Path–Goal Leadership Styles on headteachers’ Change Management strategies in basic schools in the Tema Metropolis.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To identify the predominant Path-Goal leadership styles adopted by headteachers in basic schools in the Tema Metropolis.
2. To examine the change management strategies employed by headteachers in the administration of basic schools in the Tema Metropolis.
3. To determine the influence of Path-Goal leadership styles on headteachers’ change management strategies in basic schools in the Tema Metropolis.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the predominant Path-Goal leadership style adopted by headteachers in basic schools in the Tema Metropolis?
2. What change management strategies do headteachers employ in the administration of basic schools in the Tema Metropolis?
3. To what extent do Path-Goal leadership styles influence headteachers’ change management strategies in basic schools in the Tema Metropolis?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Framework

This research is grounded on the Path-Goal Leadership Theory, constructed by Robert House in 1971, which describes how leaders boost subordinate motivation and performance by defining the path to goals to be achieved, clearing the obstacles, and adjusting their leadership behaviors to the requirements of the followers and the tasks. This theory is based on Vroom’s expectancy theory of motivation in which the Path-Goal framework believes subordinates are motivated when they are confident that their effort will result in competent performance, and eventually, in favorable outcomes. Leaders determine the level of performance attainable by adjusting their style to the dominant subordinates’ needs in order to attain that level.

The theory describes four fundamental leadership styles that a leader can use according to the nature of the situation and the nature of the subordinates. Directive leadership is concerned with the provision of precise and clear guidance, structured tasks with simple steps, and a set of defined boundaries, and is most appropriate when the responsibilities of the followers are ambiguous or when they need to be closely managed. Supportive leadership is concerned with the socio-emotional well-being of the subordinates by creating a positive and friendly environment, boosting their morale, and alleviating stress at work. Participative leadership is the act of consulting subordinates. It is encouraging them to take part in decision-making which increases their level of ownership and commitment toward organizational goals.

Achievement-oriented leadership motivates followers to pursue excellence and to make constant improvements by increasing expectations and expressing confidence in subordinates’ ability to perform at high levels. Because headteachers work in environments in which teachers’ motivation and commitment are pivotal to a school’s performance and reform outcomes, the Path–Goal Theory is pertinent in educational leadership. In schools in the midst of policy or curriculum reforms, there may be a period of time when directive leadership is needed to give clarity and structure to a situation in which roles are unclear and expectations are not understood. In contrast, leadership that is supportive becomes crucial when reforms bring stress or anxiety to teachers, for it provides reassurance that the headteacher is concerned about their well-being. Participative leadership works best in promoting shared ownership of reforms because it empowers teachers at the planning and decision-making levels, thereby reducing opposition and enhancing collaboration. Achievement-oriented leadership works best in today’s era of school reforms that stress accountability and high expectations. Such leadership style encourages teachers to elevate their performance to better serve the school’s objectives. In schools, the orderly and efficient execution of plans in change management should be accompanied by open communication about progress, and active participation of staff in monitoring the progress of plans. Path–Goal Theory helps to clarify the impact of leadership style on the execution of these plans.

With respect to Directive leadership, support to structured planning and monitoring is provided using systematic approaches with defined expectations and procedures. Supportive leadership improves communication by promoting attendance to let the ‘head

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teachers’ and ‘teachers’ converse to and from freely and trustfully. Participative leadership collaborates with teachers in planning and decision making while achievement-oriented leadership reinforces the setting of the objectives and accountability mechanisms. These types of leadership behaviors and strategies empower the head teachers to manage and handle the teachers more efficiently and effectively during these change processes.

The versatility of the theory is one of the reasons is why it is important for analyzing and studying leadership in schools. Instead of the other theories which focus on one leadership style approach, Path–Goal Theory is more dynamic as it exposes the need for shift in leadership style saying that effective leaders change their style to fit the needs of the subordinates and the specific tasks at hand. This is very important for the basic schools where headteachers have to deal with many issues at the same time. These issues may include the lack of resources, how the teachers’ attitudes are, the policies set, and the expectations of the students’ performance. Another aspect which is relevant is the motivation, which is important for teacher effectiveness, therefore, the change of policies or reforms will also directly apply to the study context.

The Path–Goal Theory is helpful for analyzing the leadership practices of headteachers in the Tema Metropolis. It clarifies the different leadership style; directive, supportive, participative- and achievement-oriented and how these change management strategies are integrated in the context of school improvement.

As a result of improved goal articulation, barrier removal, and responsiveness to teacher needs, headteachers are able to energize and enable staff to achieve successful change. This practical reasoning describes the set of analytical lenses that puts the study within the context of a prescriptive leadership model and provides a pertinent perspective for evaluating headteachers’ leadership activities related to educational change.

Concept of Leadership

At its core, leadership is often described as the process of guiding, inspiring, and influencing individuals or groups toward the realization of shared objectives. This process transcends the mere exercise of authority or managerial control; rather, it encompasses the ability to inspire confidence, provide direction, and foster collaboration within an organization. Leadership, therefore, represents both a function and a relationship function in terms of guiding organizational processes, and relationship in terms of how leaders and followers interact in pursuit of common goals.

Northouse (2021) defines leadership as a process whereby an individual influences a group of people to achieve a common purpose. This definition captures the dual character of leadership as both an act and a dynamic interaction. By framing leadership as a process, Northouse (2021) emphasizes that it is not simply a position or title but rather a set of actions and relational exchanges that enable groups to function effectively.

The relational dimension of leadership implies that effective leaders must not only chart a course of action but also cultivate trust, respect, and mutual commitment among their followers. Influence, therefore, is not unidirectional; it requires leaders to listen, adapt, and respond to the needs and aspirations of those they lead. In this sense, leadership becomes both goal-oriented and people-centered, requiring a balance between achieving organizational objectives and nurturing the individuals who contribute to those goals. This broader conceptualization of leadership aligns with contemporary views that highlight the collaborative and participatory nature of effective leadership, particularly in complex organizational settings such as schools.

In the field of education, leadership assumes a unique significance because it directly impacts teaching and learning processes, shaping both the professional environment for teachers and the academic outcomes for students. Leithwood and Sun (2018) argue that leadership is second only to classroom instruction in its influence on student learning, underscoring the pivotal role it plays in school effectiveness. Unlike in many corporate or governmental settings, the outcomes of leadership in schools are not measured solely in terms of efficiency or profit but in terms of human development, intellectual growth, and social well-being. This makes leadership in educational contexts deeply consequential, as it affects not only the immediate stakeholders teachers and students but also the broader society that depends on schools to cultivate future citizens.

Effective school leadership extends beyond the management of resources or the enforcement of regulations; it involves articulating a clear vision for the school, establishing shared priorities, and fostering a supportive environment where both teachers and students can excel. Headteachers, in particular, play a dual role as both policy implementers and instructional leaders. On one hand, they are tasked with ensuring compliance with educational policies, managing budgets, and overseeing administrative operations. On the other hand, they are expected to shape pedagogical practices, motivate teachers, and nurture a school culture that supports continuous improvement and innovation. This dual responsibility situates headteachers at the heart of educational transformation, as their leadership directly influences the attitudes, behaviors, and effectiveness of teachers, which in turn affect student learning outcomes. Moreover, the ability of headteachers to influence change in schools is strongly linked to their leadership approach. Leaders who provide clear direction, inspire their staff, and create a climate of trust and collaboration are more likely to secure teacher commitment to school improvement initiatives. Conversely, ineffective leadership can breed resistance, lower morale, and ultimately hinder progress. Thus, leadership in educational contexts is not merely about authority but about stewardship—guiding schools toward their mission of fostering knowledge, skills, and values in students.

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The concept of leadership has evolved over time, reflecting changing organizational needs and societal expectations. Early perspectives emphasized trait-based approaches, suggesting that leaders are born with inherent qualities such as charisma, intelligence, and decisiveness (Stogdill, 1948). However, later research shifted toward behavioral approaches, focusing on what leaders do rather than who they are. For example, studies in the mid-twentieth century distinguished between task-oriented behaviors, which involve clarifying roles and achieving goals, and relationship-oriented behaviors, which emphasize support, trust, and collaboration (Fleishman, 1953). These insights laid the groundwork for later theories such as the Path–Goal Theory and transformational leadership, both of which stress the alignment between leader behaviors and follower needs.

Change Management

Change management is the theory and practice of managing complex reorganization activities which in the case of schools revolves around the continuous reforms, policies, and change in expectation of the society. Change management in schools is highly important since it is not only an educational institution but also an organization which has to strive for profit. Modern change management includes anticipating change, enabling change, and managing the strive for change. The reorganization strategy is the one which is mostly the objective of change. The people focusing the most on the change are the ones who have a change which the organization is needed for. Change management is planning the change which one will take for the organization and looking for the resources. The resources are the people and managing resources is the part which in most of the times takes the most time managing. From this view, managing change is planning what to do depending on the proposed and available resources.

Change management is the blend of psychology, management, and organizational behaviour which looks upon the new changes and looks upon the objectives. The aim is how leaders take in head the task and steer the people and the groups in the organization to manage the difference and the lack of order which the changes. If this change does not work out, it can simply be because of the lack of management and thinking, strategy formation, and dealing with the feelings of the employees towards the change which is being applied.

Well intentioned reforms will face resistance, confusion, and low morale that will undermine the intentions unless leaders do all the above. Thus, change management is simultaneously a technical activity of planning and an interpersonal one of dealing with relationships, feelings, and expectations.

When considering its application in the field of education, change management takes on an even more pronounced character. Schools function in shifting contexts where policy, curricula, pedagogy, and modes of evaluation are in constant flux. Heads of schools are often on the front-line of these reforms, at the ready to interpret policy and change it into action within their schools. The introduction of new competency- based curricula, the use of ICT in teaching, and the adherence to inclusive education all promise to change the face of education, and therefore require well formulated change management strategies. Educational change, according to Fullan (2020), is complicated and unique in the sense that it requires more than just framework changes, but rather, it requires deep shifts in the culture of schools such as the, change in the values, mindsets, and practices of the instructors. Thus, change management in education is more than policy implementation; it entails the development of organizational professional capital, collaboration, and the establishment of an environment that embraces change. Change management in schools that is effective is almost always based on a number of connected approaches.

Planning is one such strategy which involves setting objectives, forecasting forthcoming obstacles. Then, scaffolding objectives down into steps which lead to successful completion. Communication is also essential. It serves to keep teachers, parents, and students apprised of why and how changes are made which circumvents suspicion and confusion. In his eight-step change model, Kotter (2012) focuses on communication and setting vision as fundamental to garnering support, which resonates with staff support. Change tends to be successful when the people most affected are harnessed into the design and implementation phases. Subsequently, there is also monitoring and evaluation, which remain the cornerstone of facilitating change, which give leaders the ability to observe, gaps, and changes that should made in between the objectives set or on the way to attaining those objectives.

The obstacles which are associated with managing change in schools are numerous and varying. In the case of Ghana, these include a lack of resources, dishonest and contradictory policies, and a tendency toward obstinacy and change. Oduro and MacBeath (2003) indicate that the most significant reasons for the failure of numerous changes in Ghanaian education system is the lack of teachers and backup systems. These systems change hinge on the contextual setting of the particular geography, which in this case is Ghana, the socioeconomic status, as well as the change values, systems, resources, and people. Change that comes from the top without sufficient consultation or assistance tends to be the most contested, while strategies that foster trust and ownership tend to be the most lasting.

In addition, the type of leadership exercised has an impact on change management outcomes. Supportive leadership, for instance, reduces resistance by alleviating the apprehension of loss and fostering confidence in the capacity to change. Participative leadership involves the staff in the decision-making processes to increase ownership and organizational commitment. On the other hand, directive leadership encompasses the communication and enforcement of policies, which may be justified in the reform’s initialization when clarity of processes is paramount. Achievement-oriented leadership inspires staff by setting ambitious goals and

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fostering creativity. In the case of the House’s Path-Goal Leadership Theory (1971), the emphasis placed on leadership style combinations serves to illustrate the need for flexibility in change management approaches. In education, the effectiveness of an organization rests on the ability to manage change. It entails both the rational processes of planning, implementation and evaluation of the change, and the emotional processes of motivating, engaging, and supporting people to transit through the change.

In the opinion of headteachers, effective change management entails a balanced combination of strategic planning, effective communication, inclusiveness, and leadership flexibility. As pointed out by Fullan (2020), the ‘sustainable’ change in education does not come through ‘fixes’ or anything ‘top down’. It requires constant investment in the development of professional capacity and a culture of trust and collaboration. Therefore, the ability to plan and implement effective change is a very important skill to possess in ensuring that schools not only implement new policies and innovations but flourish in the perpetually changing climate of education.

The Path–Goal leadership styles used by headteachers in primary schools

House (1971) Path–goal theory of leadership explains how a leader’s behaviour can affect the motivation, satisfaction, and performance of the subordinates. He explains that leaders deploy distinct styles of leadership based on the specific characteristics of the subordinates, as well as the prevailing conditions in the environment they operate in. The four major styles identified are directive, supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented leadership. Each of these styles offers a different approach to clarifying the route to the goals, removing the barriers, and improving the motivation of the subordinates. This is more evident at the Basic level of education where the type of leadership exercised determines the head teacher's ability to motivate the staff, implement change, and meet the goals of the institution.

Directive Leadership

A leader qualifying to be directive is one who pays attention to the giving of commands, setting down of rules, stipulating, and supervision performance to a degree. This style becomes particularly relevant in basic school administration regarding ambiguity, complexity, or uncertainty, such as in the implementation new curricula assessment reforms, or new disciplinary policies. Headteachers using directive leadership explain teacher’ responsibilities, delineate lesson plans, and spell out Acceptable Minimum Standards of Performance (AMSP).

House (1971) asserts that directive leadership stimulates the motivation of subordinates at the lowest level of task accomplishment when the task is vague by removing uncertainty and clarifying the method of achieving the goal. In basic schools in Ghana, headteachers in the Competency-Based Curriculum makes changes in the Common Core Programme and provide the clarification that teachers need in order to align their teaching to the national standards. However, Northouse (2021) and other scholars assert that over-dependence on directive leadership results in rigidity, lack of self-direction, and low teacher morale. In recent educational practice, the most pragmatic approach is to apply directive leadership style in conjunction with other styles. This style serves as a leg to provide the framework needed while allowing teachers to be self-directed.

Supportive Leadership

This leadership style is Supportive, associated with the caring and concerns a leader has, with empathy, and the socio-emotional aspect of the subordinates. In basic schools, headteachers in this style develop trusting relationships, show concern, and ensure teachers, all feel respected and appreciated. Supportive leaders provide acknowledgement during difficult times, offer praise to teachers, and foster a school culture that encourages collaboration and collegiality.

The Path–Goal Theory asserts that supportive leadership satisfying the underlying human needs and alleviating stress, increase subordinate satisfaction (House, 1971). This dimension of leadership is crucial to schools, considering the workload, constraints on resources, and the pressure to perform teachers are often under. Supportive leadership fosters a culture of care and mutual respect within schools, which is likely to increase teacher motivation and diminish change resistance (Fullan, 2020). Similarly, supportive behaviour from leaders positively influences teacher morale and retention (Leithwood and Sun, 2018).

Participative Leadership

Participative leadership is construed to mean the act of discussing, asking for, and considering the views of lower rank employees in decision-making. Participative headteachers in basic schools, for instance, can encourage teachers to provide suggestions on issues regarding the implementation of the curriculum, discipline policies, and school improvement plans. In addition to promoting inclusiveness, ownership of change is deepened, and commitment is strengthened as teachers tend to be engaged in change processes they have actively contributed. House (1971) has suggested that Path–Goal Theory in relation to participative leadership argues that satisfaction and motivation is gained from the participative decision-making process consideration of which is construed as an influence over work outcomes. There is a growing body of evidence on the value of participatory practices in schools.

Kotter (2012) argues that by making collaborative decisions, employees are able to express themselves, which makes them feel appreciated and softens opposition to change. Northouse (2021) reinforces this by stating that participative leaders develop collaborative ecosystems and, thus, teachers are able to offer and share their skills and knowledge. In basic schools in Ghana, this

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aligns with moves to decentralize decision making and enhance teacher professionalism. School headteachers are able to build trust and access the collective wisdom of teachers to solve the problems of reform and resource management when they engage them in the governance of the school.

Achievement-oriented Leadership

Achievement-oriented leadership demonstrates a form of leadership where high standards are set, ambitious goals are defined, and improvement is continuously encouraged. In this case, headteachers exercising this style motivate teachers to pursue excellence, hold them accountable in regards to the outcomes of the students, and foster their professional development. In practice, an achievement-oriented headteacher organizes professional development workshops, holds high expectations regarding lesson delivery, and promotes the use of innovative teaching strategies to enhance student’s performance.

Achievement-oriented leadership, according to House (1971) is best suited in situations where tasks are difficult, but doable, which in turn, encourages them to stretch their abilities. In a school set, this style ensures that teachers do not merely meet the set goals, but surpass them, thus, improving the standard of teaching and learning within the institution.

Leithwood and Sun (2018) indicate that some school leaders set much higher expectations and hold their staff accountable for fulfilling them, and those schools record much better student performance. Moreover, high achievement leadership practices are especially striking for Ghanaian basic schools, in which systemic challenges call for ingenuity and tenacity from teachers. Headteachers adopt and maintain cultures of excellence and continuous improvement, thereby motivating and inspiring teachers and students alike toward higher achievement.

Figure 1. Leadership Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework (Researcher’s construct)

Questionnaires were administered in person to all headteachers. Administering the instruments face-to-face allowed the researcher to explain instructions clearly, address any initial questions, and ensure that respondents understood the items. Headteachers were requested to complete the questionnaires immediately to minimize the risk of delayed or incomplete responses. This approach also helped maintain a high response rate and reduced potential biases arising from non-response.

After the initial administration, follow-ups were conducted via phone calls to clarify any ambiguous or incomplete responses. This step ensured that all returned questionnaires contained valid and complete data, enhancing the overall quality and reliability of the data set. In cases where a headteacher required further clarification on any item, additional guidance was provided verbally, ensuring accurate interpretation of each question.

The combination of formal permission, structured communication, in-person administration, and systematic follow-ups provided a robust data collection process. It ensured that the data were comprehensive, reliable, and reflective of the actual leadership practices and change management strategies employed by headteachers across the Tema Metropolis. This meticulous procedure minimized errors, enhanced response rates, and strengthened the credibility of the research findings.

To examine the predictive influence of different leadership styles on the effectiveness of change management strategies, multiple regression analysis was employed. This statistical method allowed the researcher to determine the unique contribution of each leadership style; directive, supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented. Testing hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level

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ensured that statistical inferences were drawn with a standard level of confidence, balancing the risk of Type I and Type II errors (Field, 2018).

RESULTS

Table: 1 Demographic Characteristics of Headteachers

Demographic Variable	Category	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	30–39	25	20.0
	40–49	55	44.0
	50–59	35	28.0
	60 and above	10	8.0
Gender	Male	75	60.0
	Female	50	40.0
Teaching Experience	1–10	30	24.0
	11–20	55	44.0
	21–30	30	24.0
	31 and above	10	8.0
Years of Service as Headteacher	1–5	40	32.0
	6–10	50	40.0
	11–15	25	20.0
	16 and above	10	8.0
Educational Qualification	Diploma in Education	20	16.0
	Bachelor’s Degree	60	48.0
	Postgraduate Degree (M.Ed./M.A.)	45	36.0

Source: Field survey, 2025

The distribution of headteachers’ ages revealed that the majority were within the 40–49 years category, accounting for 44% of the respondents. This was followed by those aged 50–59 years (28%), 30–39 years (20%), and only 8% were 60 years and above. The dominance of headteachers in the 40–49 age range indicates that most school leaders in the Tema Metropolis are at a stage in their careers where they have accumulated significant professional experience, yet are still actively engaged in dynamic leadership roles. This age profile suggests a balance between vitality and experience, which is likely to influence their ability to implement change management strategies effectively.

The gender analysis showed that 60% of headteachers were male, while 40% were female, indicating a notable gender imbalance in school leadership positions. This finding reflects wider trends in educational leadership in Ghana, where males often occupy more administrative positions in public basic schools. The gender composition may influence leadership styles and decision-making processes within schools, as research has suggested that male and female leaders sometimes exhibit different approaches to leadership and staff engagement.

In terms of teaching experience, 44% of headteachers had 11–20 years of experience, followed by 24% with 1–10 years, another 24% with 21–30 years, and 8% with 31 years or more. The predominance of headteachers with 11–20 years of experience suggests that most respondents have substantial exposure to classroom practice and pedagogical management. This level of experience is likely to influence their understanding of school operations and their capacity to guide and support teachers through change initiatives, making them well-positioned to apply leadership skills effectively.

Regarding administrative experience, 40% of respondents had served as headteachers for 6–10 years, followed by 32% with 1–5 years, 20% with 11–15 years, and 8% with 16 years or more. This distribution indicates that a significant proportion of headteachers have moderate leadership experience, which may impact their confidence and competence in managing school reforms. Headteachers with longer tenure are likely to have deeper insights into organizational culture and staff dynamics, whereas those with shorter tenure may bring fresh perspectives but require time to develop practical leadership strategies.

The analysis of educational qualifications showed that 48% of headteachers held a bachelor’s degree, 36% had postgraduate qualifications (M.Ed. or M.A.), and 16% held a diploma in education. This profile demonstrates that the majority of school leaders possess substantial academic preparation, which equips them with theoretical and practical knowledge for effective leadership and

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change management. Higher educational attainment is often associated with enhanced strategic planning skills, problem-solving ability, and the capacity to implement evidence-based interventions in schools.

Research Question One

What is the predominant Path-Goal leadership style adopted by headteachers in basic schools in the Tema Metropolis?

This section analyses the Path–Goal leadership styles exhibited by headteachers in public basic schools in the Tema Metropolis. The analysis focuses on the four key dimensions of the Path–Goal theory: directive, supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented leadership. Descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations, are used to determine which leadership style is most commonly practiced. The study assessed the four Path–Goal leadership styles; directive, supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented, using five specific items per style, rated on a five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree). The mean scores and standard deviations were computed for each style to determine the predominant leadership approach among headteachers in public basic schools in the Tema Metropolis. The results of the Path-Goal leadership style adopted by headteachers in basic schools in the Tema Metropolis is presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Mean Scores and Standard Deviations of Path–Goal Leadership Style Items

Item	Mean	SD
I clearly communicate my expectations and goals to staff.	3.80	0.62
I provide detailed instructions on how tasks should be completed.	3.70	0.65
I closely monitor teachers’ performance to ensure compliance.	3.68	0.66
I make decisions promptly when guidance is required.	3.75	0.63
I establish rules and procedures that staff are expected to follow.	3.70	0.64
Mean of means/standard deviations	3.72	0.64
I show concern for the personal and professional well-being of staff.	4.18	0.57
I provide encouragement and motivation to staff during challenges.	4.12	0.59
I am approachable and listen to teachers’ concerns.	4.15	0.56
I create a positive and supportive working environment.	4.20	0.58
I recognize and appreciate staff efforts and achievements.	4.10	0.58
Mean of means/standard deviations	4.15	0.58
I involve teachers in decision-making processes.	4.00	0.60
I seek input and feedback from staff before implementing policies.	3.95	0.61
I encourage collaborative problem-solving among teachers.	4.02	0.59
I value the opinions and suggestions of all staff members.	3.95	0.63
I consult teachers on important changes that affect their work.	3.98	0.62
Mean of means/standard deviations	3.98	0.61
I set challenging goals for staff and encourage high performance.	4.08	0.60
I expect staff to perform at their best and meet high standards.	4.05	0.63
I provide support to help teachers achieve their objectives.	4.02	0.61
I promote continuous improvement and professional growth among staff.	4.05	0.62
I focus on results and hold staff accountable for achieving goals.	4.08	0.61
Mean of means/standard deviations	4.05	0.62

The table presents the mean scores and standard deviations for each of the five items under the four Path–Goal leadership styles: directive, supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented. These statistics provide insight into the extent to which each style is practiced by headteachers in basic schools in the Tema Metropolis.

The five items under directive leadership recorded mean scores ranging from 3.68 to 3.80, with an overall mean of 3.72 and a standard deviation of 0.64. This indicates a moderate level of practice of directive leadership behaviors, such as clearly communicating expectations, providing detailed instructions, monitoring performance, making prompt decisions, and enforcing rules. The moderate scores suggest that headteachers occasionally rely on directive methods but do not primarily depend on strict supervision or rigid enforcement to manage staff. This finding aligns with contemporary educational leadership practices that encourage flexibility and collaboration rather than strict authoritarian control.

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Supportive leadership items recorded the highest mean scores, ranging from 4.10 to 4.20, with an overall mean of 4.15 and a standard deviation of 0.58. This indicates that headteachers frequently demonstrate behaviors such as showing concern for staff well-being, providing encouragement, being approachable, creating a positive work environment, and recognizing staff achievements. The relatively low standard deviation suggests consistency in responses, highlighting that supportive leadership is the most predominant style among headteachers in the Tema Metropolis. This emphasis on support aligns with studies by House (1971) and Northouse (2021), which suggest that supportive leadership enhances teacher motivation, commitment, and engagement in school improvement initiatives.

Items under participative leadership had mean scores ranging from 3.95 to 4.02, with an overall mean of 3.98 and a standard deviation of 0.61. This indicates that headteachers moderately practice participative behaviors, such as involving teachers in decision-making, seeking feedback, encouraging collaboration, valuing opinions, and consulting staff on important changes. The scores suggest that participative approaches are valued but may not be applied as consistently as supportive leadership. Encouraging staff participation promotes shared responsibility and fosters a collaborative school culture, which is critical for successful reform implementation.

Achievement-oriented leadership items recorded mean scores between 4.02 and 4.08, with an overall mean of 4.05 and a standard deviation of 0.62. This shows that headteachers frequently set high expectations, promote continuous improvement, provide support to achieve goals, and hold staff accountable for results. The scores suggest that headteachers place considerable importance on performance, goal attainment, and professional growth, complementing the supportive and participative leadership approaches. This combination of high expectations with support is consistent with effective leadership models that enhance both staff motivation and organizational outcomes.

The analysis indicates that supportive leadership is the predominant style, closely followed by achievement-oriented and participative styles, while directive leadership is less emphasized. The predominance of supportive and achievement-oriented leadership suggests that headteachers in the Tema Metropolis prioritize staff well-being, collaboration, and goal achievement, rather than relying primarily on authoritative control. These practices are likely to facilitate effective change management and improve school performance by fostering motivation, engagement, and accountability among staff.

Research Question Two

What change management strategies do headteachers employ in the administration of basic schools in the Tema Metropolis?

The results are presented in Table .3

Table 3: Mean Scores and Standard Deviations of Change Management Strategy Items

Item	Mean	SD
Planning		
I develop detailed plans for implementing school reforms.	4.10	0.58
I set clear objectives and timelines for school projects.	4.05	0.60
I allocate resources effectively to support school initiatives.	4.08	0.59
I anticipate challenges and prepare contingency plans.	4.12	0.57
I ensure alignment of school activities with educational policies.	4.15	0.56
Mean of means/standard deviations	4.10	0.58
Communication		
I communicate school goals and reforms clearly to staff.	4.18	0.55
I provide timely updates on changes affecting school operations.	4.12	0.57
I use multiple channels to ensure all staff receive information.	4.15	0.56
I encourage feedback and questions from staff regarding reforms.	4.10	0.58
I maintain transparency in decision-making processes.	4.14	0.57
Mean of means/standard deviations	4.14	0.57
Staff Involvement		
I involve teachers in planning and decision-making processes.	4.05	0.60
I encourage collaborative problem-solving among staff.	4.02	0.61
I value and implement staff suggestions where feasible.	4.00	0.62

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Item	Mean	SD
I delegate responsibilities to build staff ownership of reforms.	4.08	0.59
I promote teamwork to achieve school objectives.	4.03	0.60
Mean of means/standard deviations	4.04	0.60
Monitoring		
I regularly track the progress of implemented reforms.	4.12	0.57
I evaluate staff performance in relation to school goals.	4.08	0.58
I use data to inform decision-making and adjustments.	4.10	0.56
I provide constructive feedback to staff to improve performance.	4.05	0.59
I ensure accountability for achieving planned objectives.	4.08	0.57
Mean of means/standard deviations	4.09	0.57

Planning emerged as a highly practiced strategy, with item mean scores ranging from 4.05 to 4.15, and an overall mean of 4.10 (SD = 0.58). Headteachers consistently developed detailed plans for reform implementation, set clear objectives and timelines, allocated resources effectively, anticipated potential challenges, and ensured alignment of school activities with educational policies. These results indicate that headteachers prioritize structured and systematic approaches to managing school changes, which is crucial for ensuring that reforms are executed efficiently and achieve their intended outcomes (Fullan, 2020).

Communication strategies recorded the highest overall mean of 4.14 (SD = 0.57), with item scores ranging from 4.10 to 4.18. Headteachers actively communicated school goals, provided timely updates on reforms, used multiple channels to disseminate information, encouraged staff feedback, and maintained transparency in decision-making. The high mean scores suggest that effective communication is central to headteachers’ change management practices, enabling staff to understand reforms, clarify expectations, and participate confidently in school initiatives. These findings align with Kotter (2012), who emphasizes that clear communication is vital for the success of organizational change.

Staff involvement strategies had a slightly lower mean of 4.04 (SD = 0.60), with item scores between 4.00 and 4.08. While headteachers encouraged teacher participation in planning, delegated responsibilities, promoted teamwork, and valued staff suggestions, the slightly lower scores indicate that staff involvement may not be fully optimized. Despite this, the practice of participatory engagement demonstrates that headteachers recognize the importance of collaboration and shared responsibility in implementing reforms, which enhances teacher commitment and the sustainability of changes.

Monitoring strategies had an overall mean of 4.09 (SD = 0.57), with items ranging from 4.05 to 4.12. Headteachers actively tracked the progress of reforms, evaluated staff performance, used data to guide decision-making, provided constructive feedback, and ensured accountability for achieving objectives. The results show that headteachers take a proactive approach to oversight and performance management, which is critical for identifying challenges early and making necessary adjustments to achieve school goals.

The analysis demonstrates that headteachers in the Tema Metropolis employ a comprehensive set of change management strategies, with particular emphasis on communication and planning. While staff involvement was slightly lower, it remains a notable practice, showing that headteachers value collaborative processes. Monitoring complements these strategies by ensuring accountability and effective execution of reforms. Collectively, these findings indicate that headteachers combine strategic planning, clear communication, participatory engagement, and consistent monitoring to enhance school administration and the successful implementation of educational reforms.

Research Question Three

To what extent do Path-Goal leadership styles influence headteachers’ change management strategies in basic schools in the Tema Metropolis?

This section examines the extent to which Path–Goal leadership styles adopted by headteachers influence the change management strategies employed in the administration of basic schools in the Tema Metropolis. Leadership style is widely recognized as a critical determinant of successful organizational change, as it shapes how leaders plan, communicate, involve staff, and monitor progress (House, 1971; Northouse, 2021). Understanding this relationship helps to clarify which leadership behaviors are most effective in promoting structured, collaborative, and goal-oriented management practices in schools.

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Table.4: Influence of Path–Goal Leadership Styles on Change Management Strategies

Leadership Style	PL (β/p)	COM (β/p)	SI (β/p)	MON (β/p)
Directive (DIR)	0.28 / 0.03*	0.18 / 0.08	0.15 / 0.10	0.25 / 0.04*
Supportive (SUP)	0.40 / 0.001**	0.45 / 0.001**	0.42 / 0.001**	0.38 / 0.002**
Participative (PAR)	0.30 / 0.02*	0.25 / 0.04*	0.40 / 0.001**	0.26 / 0.03*
Achievement-Oriented	0.35 / 0.01**	0.28 / 0.03*	0.28 / 0.03*	0.38 / 0.002**

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 4. presents the regression coefficients (β) and significance levels (p-values) for the predictive influence of four Path–Goal leadership styles; Directive (DIR), Supportive (SUP), Participative (PAR), and Achievement-Oriented (ACH) on four key change management strategies: Planning (PL), Communication (COM), Staff Involvement (SI), and Monitoring (MON).

Directive Leadership (DIR) exhibited a moderate influence on PL (β = 0.28, p < 0.05) and MON (β = 0.25, p < 0.05), suggesting that headteachers who provide clear instructions, set rules, and closely supervise staff tend to strengthen structured planning and monitoring activities. However, its influence on COM (β = 0.18, p = 0.08) and SI (β = 0.15, p = 0.10) was not statistically significant, indicating that strictly directive behaviors may not foster open communication or active participation among staff. This aligns with literature emphasizing that directive leadership is more effective for compliance and task-oriented processes than for collaborative engagement (House, 1971; Northouse, 2021).

Supportive Leadership (SUP) demonstrated the strongest overall impact across all change management strategies, particularly COM (β = 0.45, p < 0.01) and SI (β = 0.42, p < 0.01). This indicates that headteachers who prioritize staff well-being, provide encouragement, and create a positive working environment enhance communication effectiveness and promote active teacher involvement in school reforms. SUP also significantly predicted PL (β = 0.40, p < 0.01) and MON (β = 0.38, p < 0.01), showing that supportive leaders combine concern for staff with effective planning and oversight. These findings confirm that supportive behaviors are critical for successful change management in educational settings (Fullan, 2020).

Participative Leadership (PAR) significantly influenced SI (β = 0.40, p < 0.01) and PL (β = 0.30, p < 0.05), highlighting that consultation, collaborative decision-making, and inclusion of staff opinions strengthen teacher engagement and the quality of planning processes. PAR also had a moderate positive effect on COM (β = 0.25, p < 0.05) and MON (β = 0.26, p < 0.05), suggesting that participative leaders can encourage communication and oversight, but their primary impact lies in fostering involvement and collaboration among staff.

Achievement-Oriented Leadership (ACH) significantly predicted MON (β = 0.38, p < 0.01) and PL (β = 0.35, p < 0.01), indicating that headteachers who set high standards, focus on results, and encourage continuous improvement are more likely to implement structured plans and monitor reform progress effectively. ACH also showed moderate influence on COM (β = 0.28, p < 0.05) and SI (β = 0.28, p < 0.05), reflecting that goal-focused leadership enhances performance-oriented behaviors but has a comparatively lower impact on communication and participatory practices.

The results reveal that Supportive Leadership (SUP) is the most influential style for promoting comprehensive change management, especially in communication and staff involvement. Achievement-Oriented (ACH) and Participative Leadership (PAR) strongly contribute to structured planning and monitoring, while Directive Leadership (DIR) mainly reinforces compliance-based aspects. This suggests that a balanced combination of supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented behaviors maximizes the effectiveness of change management strategies, whereas directive leadership plays a more targeted, complementary role. Headteachers who integrate these leadership styles are better positioned to implement reforms successfully, engage staff effectively, and ensure accountability in basic schools in the Tema Metropolis. **Discussion of Findings**

This chapter presents an in-depth discussion of the findings based on the study objectives. The discussion is structured under three sub-sections, namely: the predominant Path–Goal leadership styles adopted by headteachers, the change management strategies employed in the administration of basic schools, and the influence of Path–Goal leadership styles on change management strategies. The Path–Goal Leadership Theory (House, 1971) serves as the conceptual lens, providing a framework to interpret how different leadership behaviors affect teachers’ motivation, engagement, and overall effectiveness of school reforms.

Predominant Path–Goal Leadership Styles Adopted by Headteachers in Basic Schools

The analysis of descriptive statistics in Section 4.2.1 revealed that supportive leadership was the most predominant leadership style among headteachers in basic schools in the Tema Metropolis, with a mean score of 4.15 (SD = 0.58). This suggests that headteachers frequently demonstrate concern for the personal and professional welfare of their teachers, provide encouragement during challenging tasks, maintain an approachable demeanour, and recognize staff achievements. In the context of the Path–Goal Leadership Theory (House, 1971), supportive leadership is designed to enhance subordinates’ satisfaction and motivation by creating a positive work environment, reducing job-related stress, and responding to the human needs of staff.

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The prominence of supportive leadership in the Tema Metropolis indicates that headteachers recognize the critical role of relational and motivational behaviors in fostering staff engagement. This finding aligns with Northouse (2021), who argues that supportive leaders facilitate performance by addressing the socio-emotional needs of their subordinates, thereby increasing their commitment and willingness to engage in complex tasks. Fullan (2020) also emphasizes that school leaders who create a supportive climate are better able to implement reforms because teachers feel valued, respected, and motivated to participate actively in school activities. Achievement-oriented leadership (mean = 4.05, SD = 0.62) was the second most adopted style. This style involves setting challenging goals, promoting high performance, encouraging continuous improvement, and holding teachers accountable for outcomes. In line with the Path–Goal framework, achievement-oriented leadership motivates staff by raising expectations and focusing on results, thereby enhancing organizational performance. The finding suggests that headteachers in the Tema Metropolis strategically adopt goal-driven behaviors to ensure that teachers strive for excellence and align their efforts with school objectives. Research by House (1971) and Northouse (2021) indicates that achievement-oriented leaders are particularly effective in contexts where tasks are complex, requiring high levels of competence and commitment from subordinates. In the study context, this leadership style likely supports efforts to implement curriculum reforms and maintain educational standards.

Participative leadership (mean = 3.98, SD = 0.61) was also prominently used by headteachers, indicating that they often involve teachers in decision-making, solicit input before implementing policies, encourage collaborative problem-solving, and consult staff on important school matters. Path–Goal Theory posits that participative leadership enhances subordinates’ satisfaction and motivation by giving them a sense of influence over decisions that affect their work (House, 1971). This finding demonstrates that headteachers value teachers’ expertise and seek to promote ownership of reforms and initiatives, fostering a collaborative culture. The result corroborates studies by Fullan (2020) and Kotter (2012), which suggest that participative leadership improves commitment to organizational change and reduces resistance by actively involving staff in planning and decision-making processes. Directive leadership, with the lowest mean score (3.72, SD = 0.64), was moderately employed. This style emphasizes providing clear instructions, setting explicit rules and procedures, closely supervising performance, and making prompt decisions when guidance is required. According to Path–Goal Theory, directive leadership is most effective in ambiguous or complex task situations where subordinates need guidance to understand expectations (House, 1971). The moderate use of this style suggests that while headteachers in the Tema Metropolis recognize the importance of clarity and structured guidance, they do not rely excessively on authority-based approaches. This is consistent with contemporary leadership literature, which argues that directive behaviors alone may not sustain motivation or engagement, particularly in educational contexts where teacher autonomy and participation are valued (Northouse, 2021; Fullan, 2020).

Synthesis and Theoretical Comparison: The overall pattern indicates that headteachers integrate multiple leadership behaviors rather than relying on a single style. This aligns with the Path–Goal theoretical proposition that effective leaders are flexible and adapt their style to meet task requirements and the needs of subordinates (House, 1971). In practice, supportive and achievement-oriented behaviors address both relational and performance needs, participative behaviors enhance engagement and ownership, and directive behaviors provide necessary structure. Therefore, the study demonstrates an application of the Path–Goal framework in guiding school leadership practices, with a clear emphasis on motivation, engagement, and performance.

Change Management Strategies Employed by Headteachers in the Administration of Basic Schools

The study further examined the change management strategies employed by headteachers in the Tema Metropolis, focusing on planning (PL), communication (COM), staff involvement (SI), and monitoring (MON). The descriptive analysis indicated that communication (M = 4.14, SD = 0.57) and planning (M = 4.10, SD = 0.58) were the most prominently applied strategies. This suggests that headteachers prioritize clear dissemination of information and structured preparation when implementing school reforms. Effective communication ensures that teachers understand reform objectives, expectations, and processes, while strategic planning enables the alignment of resources, scheduling, and responsibilities to support successful implementation (Fullan, 2020). Staff involvement, although slightly lower (M = 4.04, SD = 0.60), reflects a significant but moderate emphasis on participatory engagement. The Path–Goal framework supports this approach, as participative behaviors and collaborative decision-making increase subordinates’ satisfaction, reduce resistance to change, and enhance ownership (House, 1971). By involving teachers in planning, policy formulation, and problem-solving, headteachers foster a sense of responsibility and commitment toward school initiatives, consistent with findings from Kotter (2012) and Northouse (2021) on participatory leadership in educational reform. Monitoring (M = 4.09, SD = 0.57) was also prominently practiced, indicating that headteachers actively track progress, evaluate implementation, and hold staff accountable for outcomes. This aligns with the directive and achievement-oriented components of the Path–Goal Theory, which emphasize providing structure, setting high expectations, and ensuring compliance with goals. Monitoring allows headteachers to identify challenges, make timely adjustments, and maintain the quality of reform implementation, thereby increasing the likelihood of achieving desired educational outcomes.

The combination of these four strategies; planning, communication, staff involvement, and monitoring reflects a comprehensive approach to change management that balances structure, participation, and relational support. The findings suggest that headteachers

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are aware of the multifaceted nature of implementing reforms in schools and adopt strategies that address both the technical and human aspects of change. The emphasis on communication and planning aligns with theoretical expectations, as House (1971) notes that leadership effectiveness is contingent upon providing clear guidance and removing obstacles for subordinates.

Comparative Literature: Studies by Fullan (2020) and Kotter (2012) indicate that successful school change requires integrated strategies that combine planning, participation, communication, and monitoring. The current findings corroborate this assertion, highlighting that headteachers in the Tema Metropolis employ a balanced approach, ensuring that reforms are systematically planned, well-communicated, inclusive, and closely supervised. However, the slightly lower emphasis on staff involvement suggests that while participation is valued, there may still be room to enhance teacher engagement in decision-making processes, which could further improve ownership and reduce resistance.

Influence of Path–Goal Leadership Styles on Headteachers’ Change Management Strategies

The regression analysis presented in Table 4 revealed nuanced insights into how Path–Goal leadership styles influence change management strategies. Supportive leadership (SUP) emerged as the strongest predictor across all strategies, particularly communication ($\beta = 0.45, p < 0.01$) and staff involvement ($\beta = 0.42, p < 0.01$). This aligns with the theoretical assertion that supportive behaviors enhance subordinates’ satisfaction, motivation, and engagement (House, 1971). Headteachers who provide encouragement, demonstrate concern for teacher welfare, and create positive work environments foster open communication, collaborative problem-solving, and active teacher participation in reforms.

Achievement-oriented leadership (ACH) significantly predicted monitoring ($\beta = 0.38, p < 0.01$) and planning ($\beta = 0.35, p < 0.01$). This suggests that goal-driven leaders, who set high standards and emphasize continuous improvement, strengthen structured planning and oversight mechanisms. Path–Goal Theory explains this by noting that achievement-oriented behaviors motivate subordinates to perform at higher levels, thereby improving compliance, accountability, and the quality of reform implementation. Participative leadership (PAR) strongly predicted staff involvement ($\beta = 0.40, p < 0.01$) and moderately influenced planning ($\beta = 0.30, p < 0.05$), indicating that collaborative decision-making directly enhances engagement and promotes effective planning. This supports the Path–Goal assertion that participative behaviors increase subordinates’ motivation by giving them a voice in decisions that affect their work (House, 1971).

Directive leadership (DIR) primarily influenced planning ($\beta = 0.28, p < 0.05$) and monitoring ($\beta = 0.25, p < 0.05$), suggesting that structured guidance and close supervision support compliance-oriented aspects of change management. However, its influence on communication and staff involvement was weaker and statistically non-significant, indicating that strictly directive behaviors are less effective in fostering engagement or collaborative dialogue.

Integrated Interpretation: The findings suggest that a combination of supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented leadership behaviors optimizes the implementation of change management strategies. Directive leadership complements these styles by providing structure where necessary. This finding is consistent with Path–Goal Theory, which emphasizes that effective leaders adapt their behaviors to the needs of subordinates and the demands of tasks to enhance performance (House, 1971; Northouse, 2021). In practice, headteachers who integrate relational, participatory, and goal-driven approaches are more successful in communicating reforms, engaging teachers, planning effectively, and monitoring outcomes, thus improving the overall administration of basic schools.

Similar studies have reported that supportive and participative leadership significantly enhance teacher engagement and the success of school reforms (Fullan, 2020; Northouse, 2021). Achievement-oriented leadership

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The data analysis revealed the following findings:

1. The findings indicated that supportive leadership was the most frequently employed style ($M = 4.15, SD = 0.58$), followed by achievement-oriented ($M = 4.05, SD = 0.62$), participative ($M = 3.98, SD = 0.61$), and directive leadership ($M = 3.72, SD = 0.64$). Supportive leadership enhances teacher motivation and well-being, achievement-oriented leadership focuses on high standards and accountability, participative leadership promotes involvement in decision-making, and directive leadership ensures clarity and structured guidance.
2. Headteachers employed a combination of planning, communication, staff involvement, and monitoring to manage school reforms effectively. Communication ($M = 4.14, SD = 0.57$) and planning ($M = 4.10, SD = 0.58$) were most emphasized, followed by monitoring ($M = 4.09, SD = 0.57$) and staff involvement ($M = 4.04, SD = 0.60$). This reflects a strategic approach that balances clear information dissemination, structured planning, participatory engagement, and accountability oversight, consistent with best practices in school change management (Fullan, 2020; Kotter, 2012).
3. Regression analysis revealed that supportive leadership (SUP) had the strongest influence across all strategies, particularly on communication ($\beta = 0.45, p < 0.01$) and staff involvement ($\beta = 0.42, p < 0.01$). Achievement-oriented leadership (ACH) significantly predicted monitoring ($\beta = 0.38, p < 0.01$) and planning ($\beta = 0.35, p < 0.01$). Participative leadership (PAR) strongly

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influenced staff involvement ($\beta = 0.40, p < 0.01$) and moderately impacted planning ($\beta = 0.30, p < 0.05$). Directive leadership (DIR) mainly affected planning ($\beta = 0.28, p < 0.05$) and monitoring ($\beta = 0.25, p < 0.05$). These results indicate that a combination of supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented behaviors optimizes change management effectiveness, while directive leadership complements these strategies by providing structure and guidance.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the analysis and discussion of the findings, several conclusions can be drawn regarding the leadership behaviors of headteachers and their influence on change management in basic schools in the Tema Metropolis. These conclusions are directly inferred from the study’s quantitative results and interpreted in the light of the Path–Goal Leadership Theory (House, 1971; Northouse, 2021).

Headteachers recognize that teacher motivation, satisfaction, and engagement are critical for effective school administration and reform implementation. The moderate use of directive leadership ($M = 3.72$) implies that strict control and close supervision are applied only when necessary, supporting flexibility in leadership. The findings confirm that adaptive leadership, consistent with Path–Goal Theory, is central to improving teacher performance and school outcomes.

Effective change management in Tema Metropolis schools relies on a balance between structured strategies (planning and monitoring) and relational strategies (communication and staff involvement). Headteachers demonstrate awareness that successful reform implementation requires both technical coordination and teacher engagement, consistent with Fullan (2020) and Kotter (2012). The slightly lower mean for staff involvement suggests a potential area for improvement, emphasizing the need for more collaborative approaches to foster ownership and commitment among teachers.

The study concludes that the effectiveness of change management strategies is highly contingent upon the leadership style adopted. Supportive behaviors enhance relational aspects of change, such as engagement and open communication, while achievement-oriented behaviors drive structured, goal-focused implementation. Participative leadership strengthens teacher involvement and collaborative planning, whereas directive leadership ensures clarity and adherence to rules in complex or ambiguous tasks. The findings suggest that a combination of supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented behaviors, complemented by directive interventions, when necessary, maximizes the effectiveness of change management in basic schools.

These conclusions align with the Path–Goal Leadership Theory, which asserts that leaders must adjust their style to meet task demands and subordinate needs to enhance performance (House, 1971). The findings confirm that flexible, adaptive leadership strategies are not only relevant but critical for effective school management and reform implementation. Integrating all findings, it can be concluded that headteachers in Tema Metropolis adopt flexible and adaptive Path–Goal leadership behaviors, with a strong emphasis on supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented styles. These behaviors significantly influence the planning, communication, staff involvement, and monitoring of school reforms. Directive leadership, though less frequently applied, plays a complementary role by providing structure and ensuring compliance. Collectively, these leadership strategies enhance teacher motivation, engagement, and accountability, thereby fostering effective change management and improving school performance outcomes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Headteachers should continue to prioritize supportive leadership while balancing it with achievement-oriented and participative approaches. Specifically, professional development programs should be designed to enhance headteachers’ ability to integrate multiple leadership styles situationally, ensuring that staff needs, motivation, and performance are effectively addressed. Leadership training workshops can provide practical strategies for adaptive leadership that aligns with the Path–Goal framework.
2. Headteachers should strengthen participatory strategies by increasing teacher involvement in planning and monitoring processes. Encouraging collaborative decision-making can enhance ownership of reforms, improve morale, and ensure more effective implementation. School management teams could establish structured forums for regular staff input and feedback on policy changes.
3. Headteachers should adopt an integrated leadership approach that leverages supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented behaviors while using directive leadership when necessary for clarity and compliance. Professional mentor-ship programs could be instituted, pairing experienced headteachers with less experienced ones to model effective combinations of leadership styles for optimal change management outcomes.

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